

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: AMVIKO****FIRST NAME: COMFORT****PROGRAM CODE: MDIA****COURSE CODE : ACA- 401****PERIOD NUMBER: ONE (1)****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author did not use Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

INTERNATIONAL ACADEMIC WRITING

1)INTRODUCTION

International academic paper writing has taken me to another level I could never imagine in the commencement of Master of Science in Diplomacy and International Affairs (MDIA). As a new Student of Euclid University, my expectations about this course were bigger than the actual course content. This curiosity drove me into taking a longer route and approach to start the course assignment than the simplified EUCLID standard. The first question I expected to find in my own understanding was” Discuss international relations with specific reference to your own country”. Nevertheless, I had to settle in and focus on the study material.

I began the period one by systematically reading through the study material which covers the academic professional paper writing. This led me to watching the 14 minute video which provided guidance on period one to five, the on line distance learning, the duration of the study period, selection of study materials, downloading of the ACA- 401 course pack for students in remote areas who may encounter difficulty in accessing the internet and online programming. I encountered this experience whenever I travelled out of the city, poor network connections often slowed down my work, nevertheless I took the challenge positively and sought immediate solutions.

The study of the EUCLID ACA-401 coursepack for period one has broadened my understanding of how to write a professional academic paper using the 2015 EUCLID standard template. It has helped me to understand that it is important to use an appropriate technique and be consistent with the writing style and note that different writers use various styles of writing whereby they can argue, agree and disagree. This paper will focus on various writing styles, arguments, and evidence with illustrations of what other writers

have researched and written about. It will cover the introduction, research, essay writing, referencing & style of writing and conclusion.

2) RESEARCH

Research is a very important feature in academic writing which is vital for essay writing (EUCLID 2015, 2). In this paper, we draw attention to what other writers and researchers have worked on in order to build on our own ideas. I can deduce that research is a scientific study process which involves building up on new knowledge on what others had studied and compiled thereby establishing proven facts. Reading and writing are very vital in essay writing. It is through researching that we obtain knowledge and evidence which allows one to develop a thesis and argument to answer the essay question.

The process of researching requires ample time for reading which will enable one to be familiar with the topic /subject of interest thereby leading you to develop one's own ideas. The reading should be done with a purpose hence leading one to the following guiding questions:-“what do I already know, what do I need to read to answer the question, is the material useful to my topic and can I use it to support my answer”? (Ibid). I agree with this because lack of ample time will definitely affect the research process which is cumbersome; inadequate time will lead to production of poor- quality work.

“The EUCLID study pack on ACA- 401” recommended that one makes notes out of the research to guide him or her in the study process. These notes should be made after reading through a number of times but not the first reading. In addition, one is encouraged to make notes with a clear question in mind which will guide in the next steps to follow.

Research therefore involves a systematic study undertaken to obtain information about a subject/topic of ones' interest for the purpose of obtaining more data, hence it requires ample time for which one has to be prepared.

3) ESSAY WRITING

Essay writing is the next step to follow after researching the basic information needed to write on. It starts with organising the research and ideas into an answer. (EUCLID 2015, 3).

It is important to note that writing an essay requires a plan of action with guiding steps to follow. These plans include: - deciding on a possible answer to the question in terms of the research you have done, deciding on the information to use after the question, looking through the notes and choosing examples to provide evidence to support your answer, deciding on the points I will discuss and writing in point or bullet form (Ibid).

It also covers sentences which should be few and preferably short answering the question with thesis statement and providing a summary on road map keeping in mind that it should be brief (Ibid).

I do acknowledge at this point that researching, organising the ideas, planning and writing the actual essay are totally different and not easy to put together. These different steps are like building blocks which require technique to organise them to form a structure.

It is important to start the essay writing with a draft before compiling the actual write up. The essay comprises of three main parts which include the introduction, body and conclusion (EUCLID 2015, 3).

The introduction consists of the draft information and questions which were ideally formed in the researched information. It moves from general to specific while opening with a short orientation introducing topic areas with a broad general opening. It also covers sentences which should be few and preferably short answering the question with thesis statement and providing a summary on road map keeping in mind that it should be brief. The preciseness emphasized on introduction is highly noted, hence it further consists of draft information and questions which were ideally formed in the researched data (Ibid).

The body of the essay consists of paragraphs which are like building blocks in the construction of the argument. One should answer the questions by developing a discussion while showing knowledge and group of material she or he has read (Ibid).

The conclusion moves from specific to general, it should restate your answer to the question, re-summarize the main points and include a final broad statement with possible implications, future directions for research to qualify the conclusion. This is the summary of the interrelationship between the introduction, body and conclusion (Ibid).

4)REFERENCING AND STYLE OF WRITING

This is the most interesting part which I actually found challenging but interesting at the same time; the EUCLID 2015 coursepack 1 outlines the different styles of referencing and writing. It is important to start the essay writing with a draft before compiling the actual write up. The essay comprises of three main parts which include the introduction, body and conclusion (EUCLID 2015, 4).

It is one of the reasons why I took long to complete the paper apart from work related challenges. I need to be honest here and state that it took me several weeks to understand the referencing part of the paper; and yet after careful study, it is not complicated as I had presumed. Much as I had studied referencing at the undergraduate level in the writing and study skills and library and information skills, one of the formulas I can remember was “3SQR” meaning study, question and review more than once and preferably three times. I would like to appreciate the depth and scope of the EUCLID standard.

All academic essays must contain references to guard against plagiarism which is a serious academic offence (EUCLID 2015, 5) mean while it is important to appreciate the work done by other writers to build up on one's own ideas.

One should ensure that she or he is familiar with the referencing style preferred by the faculty, school or institution and most importantly the style the writer is comfortable with (EUCLID 2015, 6). I have found this very important because you cannot master all the different styles at once although with time you will be able to apply them accordingly.

The various referencing styles according to the EUCLID 2015 coursepack ACA-401 includes US and UK spelling, Turabian, Zotero to mention but a few. I have had challenges in applying the US spelling in comparison with the UK spelling owing to the background of my country Uganda which was colonized by the British before attainment of independence in 1962.

I would like to acknowledge the EUCLID standard pack which has enabled me to understand and make use of US spelling without a bias.

5) CONCLUSION

The beginning of this paper was interesting and challenging at the same time, but on the upper hand, I have learnt a lot during the study period which helped me to write this response paper one.

It was very important to follow instructions as provided in the EUCLID study coursepack of ACA-401 of 2015. The study guide that started with the 14-minute video was a great introduction which provided good guidance as I started with the study material before the writing of this paper.

This paper consists of five parts which include the introduction, research, essay writing and style of writing and conclusion.

The introduction covers the subject of the entire response paper which talks about what the writer wants to talk about with emphasis on the research topic with questions and thesis.

Research involves obtaining of information to establish the basic facts and also using data which has been provided by other authors without owning them. Referencing the source of data is important to avoid plagiarism which is an offence in any academic paper writing.

It is important to note that there are different styles of referencing but should be carefully applied basing on the requirement of every institution and what one is comfortable and familiar with.

Conclusion which is the last part of this paper is basically the summary of what I have discussed in this response paper. I would like to thank Euclid University, particularly Dr. Gulma Kabiru for the professional guidance and the tolerance of all the challenges I encountered. I believe my next response paper will be better after this experience.

REFERENCES

Euclid University. 2015. *ACA- 401 Coursepack for Period 1*. Washington DC: Euclid University Press.

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